

INTEGRATIVE EDUCATION AS THE BASIS OF A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH IN EXTRACURRICULAR MUSIC CIRCLES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13299992>

Abstract: In this thesis, integrated education in music education, in music circles, there are opinions about the basis of the complex approach.

Key words: Musical education, methodology, pedagogical process, types of musical activities, music theory.

Introduction.

The need for a comprehensive approach to the training of a music teacher is related to one of the objective contradictions of the modern pedagogical education system, that is, the conflict between the integrity of the person and the activity of the teacher, and the lack of a comprehensive course for its formation.

Over the past few decades, researchers have made many attempts to resolve this controversy based on holistic and systematic scientific principles. However, it is not always possible to clearly determine how systematic, holistic and comprehensive approaches to the process of teacher training are related to each other. Taking into account the dialectical unity of these approaches, we will try to determine their proportions based on the analysis of available data.

A detailed review of the systematic approach as one of the methodological directions of modern science belongs to the philosophers of the 20th century. The authors explain the essence of the systematic approach in one of their works as follows:

dividing the studied object into parts and studying the object reduced to the qualitative description of these parts cannot create a complete model of the object;

the specific characteristics of a complex object (system) are not limited to the characteristics of its constituent elements, but are based on the nature of the relationship between certain elements.

The systemic approach is described as a general methodological principle and is defined as follows: approaching the objects of reality as a system based on the consideration of the natural connections inherent in these systems and knowledge of practical activities. The author provides a basis for the principles of a systematic approach that should guide teachers in the knowledge of educational systems, their organization and management. Such principles: integrity, structure, interdependence of system and environment, hierarchy.

I. V. Blauberg and B. G. Yudin, who describe integral objects, their main characteristic is called integrative property, the essence of which is that the whole is characterized by new qualities and properties that are not inherent to individual parts, but arise as a result of their interaction. This important feature of holistic formation, according to the authors, allows to understand all the features of the whole.

The analysis of the literature showed that there are no serious disagreements about systematic and holistic approaches, holistic, as a rule, is considered from a systemic point of view. As for the comprehensive approach, the approach of V. I. Zagvyazinsky and I. G. Fomicheva, which we share, should be highlighted. Having studied the problem of interdependence of systemic and complex approaches, the authors come to the conclusion that there are different carriers of integrity, with a holistic approach, such a carrier is a holistic object or process that can be expressed as a system, with a complex approach, the carrier of integrity is a sub 'ekt (individual or collective) and its activity will be. According to researchers, the consistent use of a comprehensive approach allows for the optimization of educational systems and, as a result, allows for a systematic approach at the level of practical activity. It follows that the most important task of the integrated approach is: "to interact, to connect all the components of the system, to make them work in one direction, in a common direction"¹.

To justify the essence, main levels and aspects of the integrated approach to the organization of education, the purpose of the integrated approach is to ensure the optimal functioning of the educational system and how to develop the personality of students. It is possible to organize a comprehensive approach at the following levels: systems as a whole, regional educational systems, pedagogical systems. More specific aspects of this approach can be revised to ensure unity: the purpose, content and methods of education, training of schoolchildren and their practical activities, educational tools and methods, etc. Particular attention should be paid to the previous foundations of the comprehensive approach:

to know the identity of the student, the structure of his spiritual experience;
in-depth knowledge of the essence of the process of formation of the teacher's professional training.

¹ Загвязинский В.И., Фомичева И.Г. О системном и комплексном подходах в воспитании // Исследование методологических проблем комплексного подхода к воспитанию: Тезисы докладов / Под ред. З.А. Мальковой. — М.: НИИОП, 1982. - 143 с. - С. 51.

Based on this, such an approach can be called complex, which provides pedagogical conditions for the development of a whole person based on a deep knowledge of the essence of the process of professional formation, its components and factors, and the relationships between them.

The implementation of a comprehensive approach to the professional training of a music teacher is based on interdisciplinary relations. In the pedagogy of music education, the interaction of academic subjects helps students to develop fully and harmoniously, rather than receiving different impressions, so that the entire system of knowledge acquired by students is based on the principles of interdisciplinary relations. It depends on the psychophysiological characteristics of the human nervous system, and therefore it is necessary to consider the psychological basis of interdisciplinary connections.

One of the most important issues is the search for connections between the knowledge of different disciplines and the study of mental processes related to their establishment in the mind. I. M. Sechenov emphasized that a new idea can be accepted only when it becomes a part of personal experience, when new judgments are supported by what is already known. During a person's life, not a single thought passes through his head that is not created from the elements recorded in his memory.

In addition, developing his theory, he calls the formation of complex temporal communication systems in the cerebral cortex a physiological mechanism of knowledge acquisition: all education consists of the formation of temporal connections, and this is thought, thinking, knowledge. New knowledge enters into various connections (associations) with the knowledge existing in the student's knowledge obtained in the process of gathering life experience. For the establishment of the strongest temporal connections, the decisive heat has the formation of optimal foci of excitation in the cerebral cortex. When learning this new material, previously learned knowledge acts as additional stimuli that strengthen the psychological mechanisms of mastering concepts. Undoubtedly, the success of education will largely depend on the number of necessary interrelated facts and events. Thus, the need for interdisciplinary communication depends on the specific nature of thinking and is determined by the objective laws of higher nervous activity, the laws of psychology and physiology.

Developing the ideas of I. P. Pavlov, local psychologists and teachers consider the process of acquiring knowledge in close connection with their use,

that is, it is interpreted as the acquisition and application of knowledge. These views Yu. It is most fully embodied in the concept of mental activity developed by A. Samarin, and the term interdisciplinary relations was used for the first time². The theory of associations based on this concept makes it possible to determine the features of the formation of interdisciplinary associations, the mechanism of their influence, etc. Based on the classification of associations formed in students, the author identified four stages of their formation: local, private system, intra-system (or object), inter-system (as the highest level of mental activity). Local associations systems related to the acquisition of concrete knowledge contribute to the full acquisition of individual concepts. in connection with the formation of the apparatus, it combines different systems of intersystem knowledge.

Taking into account the interdisciplinary associations, it shows that the origin of education is within the discipline, since its system contains the embryos of a number of other educational disciplines. Inter-object relations allow you to look at the object from different angles and remember this phenomenon of reality more strongly.

The formation and development of the idea of interdisciplinary relations in pedagogy has a long historical path - from the initial attempts to restore the lost parallels between the disciplines studied in pedagogy to modern integrated educational systems. The idea of interdisciplinary relations in pedagogy is one of the aspects of the comprehensive approach to education and upbringing, comprehensive development of personality. Y. A. Comensky was the first to address this problem. Reflecting on the reflection of the integrity of nature in the content of the educational material, he emphasized that everything that is interconnected should be taught in the same relationship. Yes. The basis of A. Comensky's theoretical position is the principle of conformity to nature, according to which, during the educational process, students should form a holistic view of the world, because nature is a whole, and human life is subject to the laws of nature.

The validity of this approach was attributed to J. Locke, who linked the idea of generalized knowledge with the determination of the content of education, in which one subject should be supplemented with elements and facts of another. In turn, I. G. Pestalozzi, Y. A. Comenius and J. Locke revealed the diversity of relations between academic subjects. One of the main conditions for finding

² Самарин Ю.А. Очерки психологии ума. Особенности умственной деятельности школьников. - М.: Изд-во АПН РСФСР, 1962. — 56с.

relationships between objects, I. G. Pestalozzi considered the determination of the true relationships of things in nature.

The first attempt to psychologically substantiate the positive effect of interaction on learning belongs to I. F. Herbart. The teacher said that connections between academic subjects play a major role in the development of comprehensive interest in the intellectual field. Later, A. Disterweg defended the advantages of the educational science system and emphasized the need to rely on the interdependence of content-related objects at the same time.

Conclusion.

The dynamics of modern social and cultural processes determines the need of the society for a socially active person of a teacher-musician with high professionalism, the ability to direct his professional and creative potential to the wide promotion of musical skills.

In this regard, there is a need to reconsider the professional and social functions of the music teacher in music education outside the classroom. The content of the activity of a music teacher, which implies thorough musical, psychological, pedagogical and methodological training, should be closely related to the tasks of music education. The extracurricular activities of teachers and students include great reserves in introducing schoolchildren to high artistic examples of musical art.

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